

Local Extrema of apparent brightness of Earth, Mars and Pluto seen from their moons

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An observer stays in a space ship that circles round a moon.

Explanations: mag= stellar magnitude, °= deg, ' = angular minute, " = angular second
AE = astronomical unit = 149598500 km ,h=hour

Earth seen from the Moon:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Moon – Earth in AE	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°]
11.2.2017 1h - 2 h	Weaker than -1.00	<1	0.00252	0.79	1.94
26.2-27.2.2017	-16.59	99-100 decreasing	0.00250 - 0.00252 decreasing	162.92 – 179.75 decreasing	1.93 - 1.95 increasing

Mars seen from Phobos:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Phobos - Mars in AE	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°]
1.1.2017 7h - 8h	-21.44	95-96 decreasing	0.000062	155.43-156.37 decreasing	42.97
1.1.2017 11h – 12 h	-16.12	4	0.000063	23.45 -23.52 increasing	42.25

Mars seen from Deimos:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Deimos – Mars in AE	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°]
1.1.2017 2h - 4h	-19.44	96	0.000157	158.18-158.23 decreasing	16.63
1.1.2017 18h - 19h	-13.86	4	0.000157	21.48-21.51 increasing	16.63

Pluto seen from Charon:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Charon – Pluto in AE	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°]
1.1.2017 10h – 15h	-8.97	18	0.000132	49.84 – 49.85 increasing	6.68
4.1.2017 14h – 19h	-11.54	80-81 increasing	0.000132	127.51-127.53 increasing	6.68

Pluto seen from Nix:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Nix – Pluto in AE	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°]
4.1.2017 5h – 16h	-9.51	81-82 decreasing	0.000329	128.66-128.92 decreasing	2.68
16.1.-17.1. 2017	-7.10	18-19 increasing	0.000321 – 0.000322 increasing	50.95-51.04 increasing	2.74 -2.75 decreasing

Pluto seen from Hydra:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Hydra – Pluto in AE	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°]
10.1.-11.1. 2017	-8.98	81	0.000432	128.71-128.76 decreasing	2.04
29.1.-30.1. 2017	-6.45	19	0.000434 – 0.000435 increasing	51.03 – 51.07 increasing	2.02 – 2.03 decreasing

Made with Stellarium and Planetarium.